

Synthesis of Some Thiazole Schiff's Bases

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Manuscript received 27 April 1979, accepted 6 October 1979

Synthesis of some thiazole Schiff's bases have been described. Due to the presence of the azomethine linkage and of the thiazole moiety, the compounds are expected to be biologically active. Their uv absorption data have been recorded and discussed.

WITH a view to designing new anticarcinogenic agents with specific action, the concept of "latent activity" has in recent years attracted considerable attention. Thus a number of practically inert azo mustards have been prepared¹ and tested for anti-cancer activity, hoping *in vivo* enzymatic reduction of the azo linkage to active compounds and indeed some specific activity has been observed. Similarly, some Schiff's base mustards have also been subjected to clinical trials²⁻⁷. Schiff's bases without the nitrogen mustard moiety have also shown encouraging results⁸. From these and related observations it has been suggested that an azo methine linkage is perhaps an essential structural requirement for such activity. An azomethine linkage, also plays important role in other biological reactions⁹.

In view of all these, it was considered worthwhile to prepare a few Schiff's bases from a number of aminothiazoles and aromatic aldehydes having the structural feature

These compounds not only contain an azomethine linkage but also the thiazole moiety, which is associated with many compounds having biological activity¹⁰.

Experimental

Equimolecular quantities of the reactants were dissolved in ethanol and refluxed for 3 to 5 hours. In some cases, crystals were directly obtained on cooling

and after filtration they were purified by recrystallisation. In a few cases, the initial oily product was extracted with benzene, washed several times with dilute acid and water. Removal of benzene from the dried (MgSO₄) solution, gave crystals when left with the appropriate solvent.

The desired Schiff's bases were obtained in 60-76% yield, by refluxing ethanolic solution of the aldehydes and the thiazoles for some hours. The colours ranged from yellow to orange. The details are given in the Table. It may, however, be noted that the products obtained from 2-Aminothiazole, 2-Amino-6-methyl benzothiazole, 2-Amino-6-nitro benzothiazole, 2-Amino-4-phenyl benzothiazole and 2-Amino benzothiazole were oily in nature from which attempts to obtain pure crystalline materials failed in most cases.

The compounds listed in Table did not respond to the tests for either an amino-group or aldehydes and analysed correctly for C, H, and N.

Data available in literature^{11,12}, show that most of the 2-aminothiazoles absorb maximally in the region of 250-275 nm while some also give λ_{max} at regions close to 300 nm. The Schiff's bases reported herein, however, generally absorb maximally near about 300 nm, while two of the compounds show λ_{max} at 400 nm, showing clearly a definite shift of the region of maximal absorption to higher wave lengths, (cf. 9), obviously due to the extension of conjugation.

Acknowledgement

The authors thank the authorities of the Bhagalpur University and the Principal, Marwari College, Bhagalpur, for facilities.

TABLE

B=BENZYL DENEAMINO ; T=THIAZOLE ; BT= BENZOTHAZOLE ; A=BENZALDEHYDE

Sl. No.	Reactants	Name of Products	Solvent of cryst. ; M. P°C	Mol. formula Appearance	Analysis for nitrogen Req. Found	λ_{max} in nm
1.	2-Amino-6-carboxyethyl BT + N, N-dimethyl A	2-(4'-N,N Dimethyl B)-6-carboxyethyl BT	Methanol 242-43	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₂ S Yellow	11.8 12.2	298, 395
2.	2-Amino-6-carboxyethyl BT + <i>m</i> -hydroxy A	2-(3'-Hydroxy B)-6-carboxyethyl BT	Methanol 245-46	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₄ S Pale yellow	8.6 8.8	298
3.	2-Amino-6-carboxyethyl BT + <i>p</i> -nitro A	2-(4'-Nitro B)-6-carboxyethyl BT	Ethanol 241-42	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ N ₂ O ₄ S Brownish red	11.8 12.5	303
4.	2-Amino-6-carboxyethyl BT + <i>o</i> -nitro A	2-(2'-Nitro B)-6-carboxyethyl BT	Methanol 244-45	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ O ₄ SN ₂ Pale yellow	11.8 12.0	299
5.	2-Amino-6-carboxyethyl BT + <i>o</i> -chloro A	2-(2'-Chloro B)-6-carboxyethyl BT	Methanol 240-41	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ ClN ₂ O ₄ S Brownish yellow	8.1 8.3	298
6.	2-Amino-6-carboxyethyl BT + A	2-(B)-6-carboxyethyl BT	Methanol 238-39	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₄ S Yellow	9.0 9.4	298
7.	2-Amino-6-carboxyethyl BT + 4-hydroxy-3-methoxy A	2-(4'-Hydroxy-3'-methoxy B)-6-carboxyethyl BT	Methanol 242-43	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₄ S Grey	7.9 8.2	300
8.	2-Amino-6-carboxyethyl BT + <i>p</i> -hydroxy A	2-(4'-Hydroxy B)-6-carboxyethyl BT	Methanol 240-41	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₄ S Yellow	8.6 8.9	299
9.	2-Amino-4-phenyl-5-thiacyanato T + N,N-dimethyl A	2-(4'-N,N-Dimethyl B)-4-phenyl-5-thiacyanato T	Methanol 201-02	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ N ₄ S ₂ Yellowish green	15.4 16.1	298
10.	2-Amino-4-phenyl-5-thiacyanato T + A	2-(B)-4-Phenyl-5-thiacyanato T	Methanol 197-98	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ N ₂ S ₂ Yellow	14.5 14.8	296
11.	2-Amino-4-phenyl-5-thiacyanato T + 4-hydroxy-3-methoxy A	2-(4'-Hydroxy-3'-methoxy B)-4-phenyl-5-thiacyanato T	Methanol 194-95	C ₁₈ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₂ S ₂ Yellow	11.4 11.0	275
12.	2-Amino-4-phenyl-5-thiacyanato T + <i>o</i> -chloro A	2-(2'-Chloro B)-4-phenyl-5-thiacyanato T	Methanol 193-94	C ₁₇ H ₁₀ ClN ₂ S ₂ Yellowish brown	11.8 11.6	285
13.	2-Amino-4-phenyl-5-thiacyanato T + <i>p</i> -hydroxy A	2-(4'-Hydroxy B)-4-phenyl-5-thiacyanato T	Methanol 192-93	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ N ₂ OS ₂ Brown	12.5 12.1	275, 301
14.	2-Amino-4-phenyl-5-thiacyanato T + <i>p</i> -nitro A	2-(4'-Nitro B)-4-phenyl-5-thiacyanato T	Methanol 195-96	C ₁₇ H ₁₀ N ₄ O ₂ S ₂ Orange	15.3 14.9	285
15.	2-Amino-4-phenyl-5-thiacyanato T + <i>o</i> -nitro A	2-(2'-Nitro B)-4-phenyl-5-thiacyanato T	Methanol 190-91	C ₁₇ H ₁₀ N ₄ O ₂ S ₂ Brown	15.3 15.0	297
16.	2-Amino-4-phenyl-5-thiacyanato T + <i>m</i> -hydroxy A	2-(3'-Hydroxy B)-4-phenyl-5-thiacyanato T	Methanol 201-02	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ N ₂ OS ₂ Yellow	12.5 12.9	297
17.	2-Amino-BT + N,N-di-methyl	2-(4'-N,N-Dimethyl B)-BT	Acetone 186-87	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ N ₂ S Orange	14.9 15.2	409
18.	2-Amino-4-phenyl T + N,N-dimethyl A	2-(4'-N,N-Dimethyl B)-4-phenyl T	Ethanol 255-56	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ N ₂ S Brown	13.6 13.8	308
19.	2-Amino-6-methyl BT + N,N-dimethyl A	2-(4'-N,N-Dimethyl B)-6-methyl BT	Acetone 290-91	C ₁₆ H ₁₇ N ₂ S Yellowish red	14.8 14.3	390, 400
20.	2-Amino-6-methyl BT + A	2-(B)-6-Methyl BT	Ethanol 210-12	C ₁₆ H ₁₅ N ₂ S Yellow	11.2 10.6	306

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